

**Excellence in GTA Development:
Supporting doctoral researchers
with gaining teaching opportunities
and teaching-related professional
development**

Dr Senthila Quirke - Reader in Academic Development,
Brunel University of London

Dr Alex Standen - Head, Academic Development, Eden
Centre for Education Enhancement, London School of
Economics

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Foreword

Universities have long relied on doctoral researchers to underpin their core activities: teaching and research. We have increasing evidence of the importance of doctoral researchers to research productivity and innovation (see, for example, our [UK Research Supervision Survey](#)). This report highlights the importance of doctoral researchers as teachers within higher education: for their own development, but also to enable university teaching to be as effective as it is. Given this importance, it is vital that doctoral researchers are given excellent support, training and development opportunities to become excellent teachers. This report presents the findings of a survey regarding the support and development available to doctoral researchers who become Graduate Teaching Assistants (GTAs) in UK universities, and offers recommendations to improve their experiences. Among its key findings are the following:

- GTAs are vital to the teaching landscape of universities, contributing significantly to both teaching and student learning, and their experiences in these roles enhance their own professional development. However, the quality of training and support they receive varies considerably across institutions.
- There remain inconsistencies in the training and support for GTAs across the sector, despite a general increase in support. Many institutions have mandatory training for doctoral researchers who teach, but the level of training, and the availability of mentoring and support, varies.
- The report identifies key challenges

faced by GTAs. These include a lack of teaching opportunities, difficulty balancing time and workload, issues with pay and contracts, insufficient training, and inconsistent support from supervisors.

- The report provides recommendations for institutions, supervisors, and doctoral researchers, to address the challenges. These recommendations encourage a collective approach to support GTAs, and aim for sector-wide consistency in their experience, and to recognise the contributions they make to teaching and the wider student experience.
- The report emphasises the need for a holistic approach to GTA development, including practical and discipline-specific training, mentorship, fair pay, and opportunities for professional development. It also encourages GTAs to be proactive in seeking opportunities, and supervisors to support their teaching aspirations.

We are extremely grateful to Dr Senthila Quirke and Dr Alex Standen for compiling this report. Their passion for supporting Graduate Teaching Assistants has been evident throughout this project, and it was their enthusiasm and expertise which enabled us to address this aspect of doctoral training. We hope that this report helps the postgraduate sector to be more systematic in its support for GTAs, and that it provides new ideas and insights into how GTAs can maximise the support they are given.

Dr Owen Gower, Director, UK Council for Graduate Education

1. Executive Summary

Graduate Teaching Assistants (GTAs)* are integral to the teaching landscape of universities, contributing substantially to teaching and learning, as well as the wider student experience. In turn, the experiences GTAs gain in their roles can considerably enhance their own academic and professional development. Their efficacy and success in these roles are influenced by the quality of the training they receive as well as the support system they are part of.

It has been widely recognised that the training and level of support that GTAs receive varies between institutions. The pandemic has highlighted the evolving nature of teaching approaches, underscoring the need for more comprehensive support and training for GTAs, who may be considered a vulnerable population within the HE ecosystem.

In September 2023, the UKCGE** convened a Town Hall meeting, led by Dr Senthila Quirke and Dr Alex Standen to discuss and debate the support strategies in place for doctoral researchers engaged in teaching. The aim was to understand current institutional practices, share challenges and successes, and to identify areas where effective guidance needs to be provided.

Subsequently, in April 2024, an electronic survey was disseminated to all attendees as well as the GTA Developers Network.*** This survey aimed to capture the diverse voices of all those involved with GTAs, as well as GTAs themselves. The survey sought to understand the current institutional contexts of GTA training and employment as well as the prevalent challenges as a way of generating sector-informed guidance and actionable recommendations for

good practice.

The following report presents the findings of the survey, thematically categorised, and provides tailored recommendations for HE institutions, doctoral supervisors and doctoral researchers.

Drawing on the voices of the sector, the report presents recommendations that encourage a collective approach to supporting doctoral researchers in acquiring and developing teaching-related skills. The recommendations are aimed at establishing sector-wide consistency to the experience of GTAs and at recognising and rewarding the contributions that doctoral researchers make to both teaching and the wider student experience.

*The authors acknowledge the wide variety of language used across the sector to describe this population of doctoral researchers who teach (e.g. postgraduates who teach, postgraduate teaching assistants, demonstrators, teaching associates, etc). For the purposes of this report, the term GTA will be used.

**As the representative body for postgraduate education in the UK, the UKCGE promotes the status of doctoral researchers who teach, champions good practice across institutions, and supports policies that better enable GTAs to carry out this role and institutions to support them in doing so.

***See p.3 of this report for further information about the GTA Developers Network.

2. Key Findings and Recommendations

This table summarises the key challenges in supporting doctoral researchers with acquiring or developing teaching-related skills and presents recommendations for addressing these contemporary challenges.

Together, these recommendations aim to lessen disparities, recognise and reward the contribution of GTAs, acknowledge their value as early career academics, and move towards a sector-wide approach in their support and development.

Challenges	Recommendations
Lack of teaching opportunities	Institutions should consider conducting a comprehensive assessment of teaching opportunities suitable for GTAs, potentially implementing a needs analysis within each department, college, or school to optimise the equitable distribution of GTA roles.
Balancing time management and conflicting commitments	Workload management is a critical competency for both academic and professional careers. Doctoral researchers should prioritise the development of strategies for effective time and workload management and be supported by their PhD Supervisors to achieve this essential skillset. Institutions should take into consideration PhD workload and time constraints when making teaching allocations.
Pay, recruitment processes, conditions of contract	Institutions need to ensure pay structures are fair, transparent and equitably applied, for both the training and for the GTA or equivalent roles.
Workload involved in teaching	Institutions could explore workload allocations models that are correlated to the levels of teaching that GTAs are able to offer based on their ability to meet the job description, their time constraints and remuneration. This could be achieved through workload metrics, which acknowledge visa and/or research council restrictions, and co-creating allocation allowances with the input of doctoral researchers in a way to balance productivity and well-being.
Insufficient training and/or inconsistent expectations of training	Institutions need to ensure that there is a comprehensive set of mandatory and optional professional development opportunities, complemented by regular refresher sessions. Mechanisms for documenting and confirming engagement in these initiatives should be implemented. Professional development should be aligned with established benchmarks such as the Professional Standards Framework (Advance HE, 2023) and Researcher Development Framework (Vitae).
Inconsistencies in support from supervisors	Supervisors should have an awareness of the teaching opportunities and teaching-related professional development available to their students, and include discussions about teaching in meetings - this might be in the context of students' wider professional development.
A need for mentoring	Institutions should consider coaching and/or mentoring based support to provide tailored guidance for doctoral researchers to tackle some of the challenges that are individual-specific. The use of mentors can be beneficial with Advance HE Fellowship applications.

GTAs and GTA development in the UK

GTAs are doctoral researchers who engage in teaching activities. This teaching activity may be in the form of contracted hours or more ad-hoc teaching provision; for some doctoral researchers, teaching forms part of their stipend (Slack & Powell, 2023). 'Teaching' encompasses a broad range of activities, including classroom and online teaching, seminar facilitation and lab demonstrating, as well as marking students' work and giving feedback, mentoring students, and supporting dissertations and project work. In the UK, as the number of doctoral researchers has increased, so has the number of doctoral researchers engaged in teaching activities, while challenges facing the UK higher education sector in terms of greater resource constraints and wider pressures on academics' time, have made discussions about the role of GTAs increasingly timely (UCU 2016; Winstone & Moore 2017; Clark et al, 2021).

GTAs are receiving steadily more support and training for their teaching, but there continues to be disparity both across and within institutions. In their roles as teachers, doctoral researchers might find that, institutionally, support comes from their supervisor, the module or programme lead for the courses they are teaching, a departmental mentor, the central teaching and learning centre or their researcher development team. Sector-wide, Advance HE provides a hub for development and support around their teaching practice, while Vitae supports their development as teachers as part of their broader professional development as researchers. The University and College Union (UCU) campaigns for GTAs' rights and for them to be treated in the same way as other employees and to be fully supported as members of staff.

Recognising some of these gaps and inconsistencies, since 2016, the GTA (Graduate Teaching Assistant) Developers Network has hosted events and an online community for colleagues in both departmental and central roles who work with GTAs. It represents over 50 HEIs from across the UK, seeking to enhance the work of GTA Developers through the sharing of ideas, resources and educational development practices and through providing a platform and collegial space to discuss policy and practice. Through its work, the network also aims to champion the voice of GTAs and other early career researchers in teaching roles. It supports two peer reviewed journals, *Postgraduate Pedagogies* and the *Journal of PGR Pedagogic Practice*, both of which are devoted to articulating, sharing and critically reflecting on the perspectives and experiences of GTAs.

In 2021, a report commissioned by the Higher Education Funding Council for Wales (Floyd & Hack, 2021) made a series of recommendations for Welsh universities on practice and policy around PGRs who teach, which are applicable beyond the Welsh context. This report informed the development of our survey.

Themes emerging in the literature

There has been a growth in the field of scholarship relating to doctoral researchers who teach, with predominant themes emerging around the role and identity of GTAs, and their training and preparation, both of which have implications for this report.

Much of the scholarship centring on GTAs and the GTA experience has foregrounded the liminality of GTAs' identity and role, their positioning between student, researcher and teacher, and how they perceive and navigate these roles (e.g. Muzaka, 2009; Compton & Tran, 2017; Winstone & Moore, 2016; Bale & Anderson 2022; Raaper, 2018). This 'in-betweenness' can be experienced by GTAs as both troubling and a space of possibility.

For example, in a 2023 study focused on wellbeing amongst PGRs who teach (Slack and Powell, 2023), the authors examined GTAs' identity management and identified two dominant themes: the first the 'paradox of credibility', in which GTAs reported grappling with a concern to be perceived as credible and worthy of teaching whilst also managing student expectations about their own knowledge; and the second, their desire to use their staff-student role to engage in 'approachability and advocacy' with and for students. Additionally, GTA-authored scholarship has explored how these academic identities intersect with other elements of GTAs identity, including class (Hastie, 2021), professional identities beyond academic (Parry, 2023) and nationality (Kaizuka, 2023).

Situating GTA roles against the backdrop of internationalisation in HE, Winter et al (2014) identified institutional and cultural factors governing

access to teaching opportunities, while Collins et al's study (2021) of a largely international cohort of GTAs explored 'cultural bumps' - where GTAs experience adjustment stresses transitioning into UK higher education teaching.

In terms of the training and development of GTAs, research has identified the benefits of both formalised training programmes and other support networks and opportunities. Research into a GTA training programme in Hong Kong (Shum, Lau & Fryer 2020) explored how, even within a short training course, teaching approaches can be developed and shaped. GTAs' pre-existing teaching conceptions about teaching (often based on their own experiences of being taught) are not the sole predictor of teaching approach when training has been undertaken. Rao et al (2020) argue that institutional training and development programmes can provide coordinated support, peer networks and a sense of belonging which were highly valued by the GTAs that they interviewed. Nasser-Abu Alhija & Fresko's study (2020), by contrast, highlights the importance of mentoring and professional interpersonal interactions with, for example, module leads, as essential to GTAs' development as teachers.

These emerging themes align with and support the recommendations in this report. Within the scholarship, recommendations are also made. For example, Slack and Powell's (2023) five recommendations for improving the wellbeing of GTAs are: payment appropriate to workload, the provision of CPD and training opportunities, acknowledgement of the time required for 'hidden' teaching work, provision of

mental wellbeing support, and treating GTAs as academic staff in order to facilitate agency.

research ethics and data management policies.

Methodology

An electronic survey was sent out via the UKCGE mailing list and was also distributed via the GTA Developers Network in April 2024. The survey sought to understand the current institutional contexts of GTA training and employment as well as the prevalent challenges as a way of generating sector-informed guidance and actionable recommendations for good practice. It aimed to capture the diverse voices of all those involved in GTA support, as well as the GTAs themselves.

The survey complied with the UKCGE's

Profile of respondents

Institutional affiliations

There were 28 responses, representing 21 institutions (two institutions receiving multiple responses and five not providing an institutional affiliation). Fifty-three percent of these institutions are pre-1992 institutions, 21% are post-1992 institutions and 4% are Russell Group.

Institutional affiliation of respondents

Figure 1. Institutional affiliations of survey respondents (n=28). Respondents selected from a pre-defined list of options for this optional survey question.

Roles

Job roles broadly defined included academic/education development (42%), academic and/or teaching roles (23%), researcher development (15%), GTA (12%) and university leadership (7%). In line with this, respondents' departmental or divisional role detail included academic departments, doctoral and graduate schools, teaching and learning centres, student services and senior leadership offices.

Figure 2. Categorised job titles of survey respondents (n=28). Similar titles were grouped into broader titles for clarity of presentation.

Experience of respondents

The majority of respondents (36%) had between 5-10 years' experience of working with doctoral researchers, with 21% having less than three years' experience, and 21% having more than 10 years' experience.

Years of experience of respondents

Figure 3. Years of experience in developing DRs or working as a GTA (n=28). Respondents selected from a pre-defined list of options for this optional survey question.

3. Survey Findings

Teaching activity

Respondents were asked to identify the range of roles available to doctoral researchers at their institution in relation to teaching and learning support. Alongside teaching (100% of responses), typical GTA roles included marking (93%), lab demonstrating (93%), academic support (57%), mentoring (50%), dissertation support (39%), training (39%) and language support (32%). Open text survey responses also mentioned guest lecturing, leading labs and supporting field trips.

Figure 4. Categorized responses in relation to the roles available for Doctoral Researchers.

Institutional approaches, policy and practice

When asked about policy and practice at institutional level, 71% of responses reported that their institution had an institution-wide policy on pay and conditions and no respondent reported that there was no policy, only that they were not sure if there was one.

Equally significant, 82% of respondents answered that it was mandatory in their institution for doctoral researchers to undertake training to teach; however, 14% of respondents replied that there was no mandatory training.

Availability of institution-wide policy on pay and conditions

Figure 5. Proportion of responses in relation to the availability of an institutional-wide policy. Respondents selected from a pre-defined list of options for this question.

Respondents' awareness of mandatory training for GTAs

Figure 6. Proportion of responses in relation to the availability of mandatory training for GTAs. Respondents selected from a pre-defined list of options for this question.

Formal and informal development opportunities for GTAs

Survey responses highlighted a wide variety of formal and informal development opportunities available to doctoral researchers in relation to building their teaching capabilities, including academic development workshops, institutional online resources, induction programmes (synchronous and asynchronous), non-credit and credit-bearing programmes, departmental training and mentoring.

Respondents were further invited to indicate whether this training was specific to GTAs, which was the case for a high percentage of responses - as the chart indicates:

Figure 7. Proportion of available formal and informal development opportunities that are specifically for GTAs.

In open text comments, respondents expanded on their answers, providing a snapshot of practice at a range of institutions:

We run a semester-long course consisting of 4-5 live classes, which is mandatory for all new PGRs who teach. If interested, students may continue to our PGCAPHE, through which they can obtain AFHEA or FHEA.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 500-1000

GTAs can access dedicated university-wide workshops. These are intended to cover pedagogical aspects. While effective and well-attended, these workshops remain quite general as they serve the whole institution. There is an expectation (not always met) that individual departments will provide additional detailed subject-specific training. In a few instances, teaching training is also provided at the departmental level to ensure that pedagogical concepts picked up during the workshops are contextualised with the specificity of the individual department teaching settings.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2000-2500

With regards to mentoring, it is written into the Policy that Postgraduates who teach will have a teaching mentor in their discipline, but this doesn't always happen in practice.

Post-1992 - PGR Population between 500-1000

introduction to teaching course that is open to all staff, postdocs and PhD students. We have different types of teaching available and pay rates approved by HR but we lack actual teaching opportunities for our doctoral researchers. Depending on the type of teaching, it may be compulsory to have attended to introduction to teaching course.

Post-1992 - PGR Population less than 500

I work in a central team which provides training and CPD for GTAs across all disciplines. My team also consults with departments and faculties to offer bespoke training sessions. We also provide training and CPD for academics and professional services colleagues who support GTAs within departments and faculties. We had an asynchronous programme during COVID but have moved towards more synchronous and in-person sessions to facilitate better interactions and model good teaching practice. We still have online induction/training options for those who are not able to attend on-campus training before they begin teaching. There are online resources which GTAs can access any time during the year. As part of the GTA Development Programme, we offer a dedicated pathway and mentoring for GTAs who are interested in applying for AFHEA. This runs in parallel and alongside the support for Lecturers and full-time academic colleagues applying for HEA recognition.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2500-3000

We have an annual two day

Responses also highlighted the extent to which practice can vary across an institution:

It's worth noting that in most faculties it is mandatory for doctoral researchers who teach to undertake training, but this is not the case everywhere and the level of training varies. Some faculties have specific workshops that doctoral researchers need to go on and they're not allowed to teach until they've attended. We do offer institution-wide workshops and online resources, but again, departmental/disciplinary training can vary. Similarly, I'm sure some departments do offer mentoring and guidance, but that's not an institution-wide policy.

No affiliation given

Current practice varies across the 3 faculties, for the Faculty of Science and Engineering a training programme of taught courses exists. This is soon to be rolled out across all faculties to replace the more local training courses currently provided. We also offer a mentoring programme for GTAs who are wanting to extend their learning and undertake the AFHEA.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 3500-4000

Discipline specific support and development will differ across disciplines and campuses.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 500-1000

As well as identifying new or developing approaches:

We are in a stage of transition here at [INSTITUTION]. PGRs have to attend 6-8 hours of centrally delivered prerequisite training in order to teach. This is delivered as blended learning. They should then have access to in-role support via their departments and could, until recently, optionally apply for a GTA specific credit-bearing course that also awarded AFHEA. However, a recent training needs analysis identified an institutional gap in in-role support owing to variances across departments. We have therefore withdrawn our credit bearing course from 24/25 in favour of widening reach for in-role support on an optional basis for a wider community of GTAs (online resource and application/teaching practice events). GTAs can continue to secure AFHEA through our existing accredited recognition scheme open to all staff who teach.

Russell Group - PGR population between 1000 and 1500

I co-lead [INSTITUTION NAME] [...], a cross-faculty community of practice. This is a specific development opportunity for a small group who lead this initiative every year, but also a space where PGR teacher-specific CPD is developed (for PGRs by PGRs). [...] We produce [...] an open access journal, so PGRs can learn about the editorial process and/or write and submit papers. Finally, [INSTITUTION NAME] produced an institutional survey about PGR teaching at [INSTITUTION NAME], so this provided another opportunity for CPD. PGRs at [INSTITUTION NAME] can also get involved in initiatives such as the [INSTITUTION NAME] Teaching Excellence Awards, as judges, which is a good developmental activity.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 1500-2000

Opportunities for gaining Advance HE Recognition

The majority of doctoral researchers have access to Advance HE recognition pathways within their institutions. While a small proportion (7%) cannot apply and an equal proportion (7%) were not sure, the remaining responses indicate that researchers can pursue either Associate Fellowship (AFHEA, 22%) or both Associate and Full Fellowship (FHEA, 63%), depending on their teaching experience.

Consistent with the above, and to some extent, explaining the proportions of GTA who can apply for AFHEA, the responses showed that there was a wide range of training and development opportunities in place for all staff involved in teaching but a smaller proportion of those opportunities was exclusively for doctoral researchers who teach.

Frameworks and guidelines referred to by institutions

With regards to frameworks, guidance documents and resources referred to when developing courses or providing support for GTAs, 81% of responses referenced the Professional Standards Framework, 69% referenced institutional guidance or policy and 31% referenced the Vitae Researcher Developer Framework.

Please see Appendix 1 for detailed responses of online resources, core readings and texts provided by some respondents.

Figure 8. Respondents' awareness of the possible opportunities for GTAs to apply for Advance HE Fellowship recognitions.

Figure 9. Categorized responses in relation to the different regulatory frameworks and resources (including self-generated) referenced in the development of courses and support aimed at doctoral researchers. A detailed list is available in the appendix.

Gaps and persistent challenges

One of the survey questions focused on identifying the persistent challenges that exist in relation to developing doctoral researchers' teaching skills or provision of teaching experiences. All respondents selected multiple options and some provided comments to supplement their responses.

C1. Lack of teaching opportunities

(67%): This was the most frequent response indicating a need for more opportunities to teach.

C2. Balancing time management and conflicting commitments (56%):

Many respondents (including doctoral researchers) indicated and reflected on the struggle to manage time effectively and balance teaching with other commitments.

C3. Pay (44%), recruitment processes, conditions of contract:

Several

respondents mentioned concerns about pay in relation to the training and work allocation. Relatedly, respondents also identified challenges around recruitment processes and conditions of contract.

C4. Workload involved in teaching

(44%): The workload associated with teaching and variations in requirements was another concern for some respondents (in relation to marking, supervision, mentoring).

C5. Insufficient training (30%) and/or inconsistent expectations of training:

A number of respondents reported insufficient or inadequate training or preparation for teaching roles. Relatedly, respondents also identified inconsistent expectations of training.

Other themes: The less frequent narratives included:

C6. Inconsistencies in support from supervisors:

Including a respondent

identifying supervisors preventing doctoral researchers from teaching.

C7. A need for mentoring: As well as inconsistencies in support from supervisors, respondents reported limited or lack of support from peers and the need for mentorship.

Illustrative participant comments are provided below:

Centralised provision like ours is important, because it can be a multidisciplinary opportunity for PGRs and encourage communities of practice. However, I strongly believe that better mentorship of PGR teachers in departments needs to accompany this. The difficulties I see is that it is inconsistent and that more senior colleagues (e.g. module convenors) lack time and capacity for close mentorship of these early career colleagues. Some do it (and do it well!) but it is on top of other commitments. [...] The challenge [in terms of supervisors] is that supervision often focuses on the research side of PGR experience, with teaching sometimes seen as an 'addition' (and for some supervisors, an unnecessary distraction!). PhD supervisors are also not always teaching themselves, therefore are not in the best position to advise.

Pre-1992 institution - PGR population between 1,500-2,000

Many PhD students would like to have stronger connections with their disciplines and departments but their teaching can often feel disconnected from their research and academic development.

Post-1992 - PGR population between 2,500-3,000

Communication between departments is essential. We're facing a significant shortfall in teaching opportunities for our PGRs. Despite having fewer PGRs compared to other universities, we're struggling to allocate teaching responsibilities to them. One major obstacle is the lack of clarity among staff regarding their authority to assign teaching duties to PGRs. Heads of departments must be actively involved and willing to allocate both time and budget for PGRs to engage in teaching activities.

Post-1992 - PGR population less than 500

4. Our General Recommendations to Address the Challenges

R1. Institutions should consider conducting a comprehensive assessment of teaching opportunities, potentially implementing a needs analysis within each department, college, or school to optimise the equitable distribution of GTA roles.

R2. Workload management is a critical competency for both academic and professional careers. Doctoral researchers should prioritise the development of strategies for effective time and workload management and be supported by their PhD Supervisors to achieve this essential skillset. Institutions should take into consideration PhD workload and time constraints when making teaching allocations.

R3. Institutions need to ensure pay structures are fair, transparent and equitably applied, for both the training and for the GTA or equivalent roles.

R4. Institutions could explore workload allocations models that are correlated to the levels of teaching that GTAs are able to offer based on their ability to meet the job description, their time constraints and remuneration. This could be achieved through workload metrics, which acknowledge visa and/or research council restrictions, and co-creating allocation allowances with the input of doctoral researchers in a way to balance productivity and well-being.

R5. Institutions need to ensure that there is a comprehensive set of mandatory and optional professional development opportunities, complemented by regular refresher sessions. Mechanisms for documenting and confirming engagement in these initiatives should be implemented. Professional development should be aligned with established benchmarks such as the Professional Standards Framework (Advance HE, 2023) and Researcher Development Framework (Vitae).

R6. Supervisors should have an awareness of the teaching opportunities and teaching-related professional development available to their students, and include discussions about teaching in meetings - this might be in the context of students' wider professional development.

R7. Institutions should consider coaching and/or mentoring based support to provide tailored guidance for doctoral researchers to tackle some of the challenges that are individual-specific. The use of mentors is also beneficial with with Advance HE Fellowship applications.

5. Recommendations for Institutions, PhD Supervisors, Doctoral Researchers

This section presents a series of recommendations, based on the findings of the survey and informed, to some extent by relevant sector-wide discussions, engagement with GTAs and literature. The recommendations are aligned to the aforementioned challenges. They are written as a call to further enquiry and action for all stakeholders in HE and the doctoral researchers.

These recommendations acknowledge:

- (1) the level of commitment and empathy to implement institution-wide equitable support mechanisms and have buy-in from all stakeholders;
- (2) the importance of personal agency and responsibility on the doctoral researchers' part in being proactive making the most of the opportunities;
- (3) the need for involvement of experts and organisations like the UKCGE to oversee and enable practice-sharing opportunities.

Recommendations for Institutions

The recommendations are clustered under the following 3 areas as identified during the thematic analysis of the survey responses as well as sector-wide discussions and engagement with GTAs.

Recruitment, Selection, Administration and Contracts:

- Implement clear guidelines on recruiting PGRs for teaching roles.
- Provide formal contracts for all forms of work allocated.
- Streamline teaching allocation across the institution.
- Reduce administrative burdens

associated with payments for teaching positions in collaboration with HR.

There should be clear guidance on the recruitment and selection of PGRs who teach including ensuring that students are given contracts for the work they are engaged in.

Post-1992 - PGR Population less than 500

There's an excessive amount of paperwork involved, often disproportionate to the actual time spent teaching. This paperwork primarily revolves around right-to-work checks and casual worker approval forms. Additionally, obtaining signatures and budget codes from various individuals adds further complexity to the process. Despite efforts to improve the process and ensure transparency, it continues to be cumbersome and inefficient. Although we have made some progress, we need to address these administrative hurdles to create a smoother experience for both PGRs and staff involved in the teaching process.

Post-1992 - PGR Population less than 500

Workload is a significant issue for GTAs, both in terms of balancing work but also over-preparation for teaching, which in turn cuts into pay rates. Training hours are not normally included in pay rates, which is a barrier for many.

Russell Group - PGR population between 1000 and 1500

Induction, Training, Workload Mentoring and Career Development:

- Provide applied and experiential training and development for teaching-related activities, that is applicable to the roles offered in the institution. Ensure the timing of training is in line with the timing of the teaching activities GTAs undertake and their own PhD timelines.
- Consider remuneration for training and preparation.
- Implement centralised training provision for multidisciplinary opportunities and departmental mentorship or other opportunities for discipline-specific training for effective application of knowledge within the discipline.
- Build in ongoing mentorship from experienced faculty to support teaching practice and Advance HE recognitions.
- Foster a sense of belonging among GTAs through peer networking and support structures.
- Acknowledge and reward GTA contributions to teaching and their role within the teaching team through institutional recognition and award activities.
- Provide opportunities for PGRs to engage in social calibration exercises and gain experience with marking and feedback practices.
- Encourage reflective practice by encouraging GTAs to critique their teaching skills through peer observation and reflection.
- Align teaching opportunities with GTAs' research expertise and career aspirations where appropriate.
- Integrate teaching experience into career development pathways for

PGRs aiming for academic careers.

I think it is important that PGRs have the same opportunity to engage in professional development of their teaching as academic and teaching staff e.g. ability to apply for institutional teaching awards

Post-1992 - PGR Population less than 500

A need for disciplinary differentiation is also a frequent point of feedback on our provision, especially around assessment and feedback, which is a challenge for centrally delivered provision that tends to be generic. We try and address this by differentiating between teaching types rather than disciplines or faculties, which is a compromise that works well enough in most cases. We find there is a risk of bias in favour of Social Sciences and Arts and Humanities teaching development provision and are currently working more proactively with the Sciences to support their specific GTA training needs (especially with respect to demonstrators)

We find there's a risk of underestimating GTAs' interest in developing understanding of wider HE issues and their relevance to their professional development (eg around sustainability or diversity and inclusion).

There is a huge thirst for peer networking and practice sharing amongst our GTAs that could be better harnessed (something we are working on with our Student Union)

Russell Group - PGR population between 1000 and 1500

Most GTAs/PGRs who teach would like the training to be practical, discipline-specific and timely. (Practical) They are often balancing teaching responsibilities with their research and so training should offer a mixture of theoretical and practical considerations that can be implemented in the classroom immediately. (Discipline-specific) Similarly, many PhD students would like to have stronger connections with their disciplines and departments but their teaching can often feel disconnected from their research and academic development. (Timely) Training should be timely, both before they begin teaching and during the academic term to be most effective. Often challenges can arise in the middle of teaching and GTAs may struggle to find support when it's needed most.

GTAs appreciated the advice they received from more experienced GTAs the most. Finding ways to co-create training, workshops and materials with experienced GTAs and to compensate them for their contributions is important.

Finally, it is important for the training to be cohesive with a clear process for registration. If the training is offered by a central team within the institution, that training needs to be designed and implemented in consultation with departments and faculties. If the registration process for teaching, payroll and training is too disconnected then it can be frustrating for GTAs to navigate these multiple systems. It should be clear to the GTAs what training is mandatory and what is optional given the demands on their time.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2500-3000

Institutions should have a clear understanding of the purpose of their particular teaching and learning systems. This clarity helps doctoral students, especially those who have no undergraduate experience at the institution, understand how they fit in the teaching and learning system and in the institution's (or department's) educational aims. This contextual understanding allows doctoral students to go on to build their own educational practices in a situated and reflective manner.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 4000-4500

Collaboration and Communication:

- Improve coordination between Researcher Development Units, Academic Practice Units, HR and academic departments to provide holistic support.
- Involve GTAs in co-creating training programmes, workshops, and teaching resources.
- Establish clear frameworks for expectations, training requirements, and support systems for GTA teaching roles.

Drawing on the findings of my fellowship on the engagements of PhD students in teaching, I identified the importance of collaborative efforts from different university departments (Doctoral College, professional development, academic staff) to provide a more effective and holistic form of support of professional development. I recommend that institutions work to join 'the broken dots' across various university departments to gain a comprehensive understanding of early career educators' strengths and needs,

offering impactful support for their professional development.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2000-2500

- Encourage students' participation in GTA work as appropriate and in line with their expertise and identified development goals.
- Offer advice or signpost to the relevant services for advice on gaining professional recognitions.

I feel that a good mentor and inclusion in normal teaching discussions at a local level is important. Central training is valuable, but it is how GTAs are supported in putting that into practice and in dealing with the challenges faced in the classroom that really makes the difference. Similarly, feeling that they belong as part of a teaching team and not just substitutes or gap-fillers, will enhance their commitment and strengthen their support mechanisms.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 500-1000

Supervisors don't seem to engage in the development of GTAs as much as we would like. We would like supervisors to take a central role in providing feedback to GTAs. We have a GTA feedback form that is sent to GTAs and their supervisors after they have taught with a member of academic staff to facilitate teaching development discussions between GTAs and their supervisors. This works well.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2000-2500

These themes highlight the need for universities to develop comprehensive programs that support doctoral researchers to be effective teachers while acknowledging their role as researchers and future academics.

Recommendations for Supervisors

The recommendations are clustered under the following 4 areas as identified during the thematic analysis of the survey responses as well as sector-wide discussions and engagement with GTAs.

Opportunities and Restrictions:

- Be aware of and signpost the availability of teaching roles across departments and programs.

There can be wide variation in the knowledge that supervisors have about teaching opportunities for PGRs in their own departments. It might be useful for supervisors or supervisory teams to be aware of what opportunities there are for PhD students to teach during their studies, the process for applying and what training is available. It has been my experience that if the supervisors are not teaching themselves, they cannot support their supervisees to access these opportunities. When the supervisors are involved with teaching, their students are often much more satisfied with their teaching experiences because their supervisors are able to guide and mentor them throughout the term. However, this means that PGRs who do not have supervisors involved with teaching can miss out on these valuable opportunities.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2500-3000

Workload Management and Support:

- Ensure that the GTA workload does not impede PhD progress.
- Encourage peer support and peer-observation.
- Facilitate doctoral researchers with achieving PhD milestones and completion while encouraging professional development.
- Prioritise the skills development and acquisition of experience rather than the expectation of acquiring paid work hours.

GTA workload should be monitored carefully with guidance on efficiencies, especially when marking for the first time.

At [INSTITUTION NAME], we require new GTAs to have their teaching observed at least once when new to role. The value doing so on a more frequent basis, including as peer observations with GTAs, cannot be underestimated.

We have one department that facilitates a GTA peer support for teaching group that is highly valued by its members and which I think could be a good model for other teams.

Based on preliminary discussion here, some science departments could reflect on the instruction they give to demonstrators that risks them assuming a passive relationship to teaching. (ie "I am just here to answer questions if a student raises their hand" versus proactively checking in on students progress on an experiment and asking probing questions)

Russell Group - PGR population between 1000 and 1500

Induction and Skills Development:

- Encourage doctoral researchers to discuss teaching aspirations early on in their PhD journey.
- Offer opportunities for shadowing new and experienced faculty members.
- Share their own teaching experiences and facilitate discussions and reflective practice.
- Encourage staying up to date with teaching innovations and recognising the relationship between teaching and research.

Where PGRs have an interest in HE teaching, support and nurture this as far as is feasible. Provide teaching mentorship (yourself or via colleagues). Consider time for training, planning and delivery, in line with academic workloads model (and with an acknowledgement that initial teaching often needs extra preparation time). Share your experiences in teaching-successes and challenges- and give time for PGWT [Postgraduates Who Teach] to discuss their experiences. Facilitate opportunities for PGWT to observe teaching in different settings.

Post-1992 - PGR Population between 500-1000

Additional Considerations:

- Create shadowing opportunities prior to GTAs commencing their roles as a form of orientation.
- Encourage open discussions about different pedagogical approaches, philosophies and tools.
- Actively support GTAs in finding paid

teaching opportunities.

- Recognise teaching as an essential skill for aspiring academics.
- Considerations for part-time doctoral researchers: Acknowledge and manage the additional time constraints of part-time doctoral researchers. Offer flexible teaching opportunities that align with their availability and interests where possible.

My recommendation would be to treat teaching and research as connected activities and perceive the two to be synergistic. A strategy that promotes the intellectual perception of teaching and research as integrated seems to be missing in HE and more work is needed to ensure that the professional development is supported effectively. Supervisors should collaborate with various departments within the university to ensure the comprehensive professional development of GTAs.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2000-2500

These themes emphasise the need for a well-structured supervisory system that provides doctoral researchers with encouragement, empathy and insight.

Recommendations for doctoral researchers and GTAs

The recommendations are clustered under the following 3 areas as identified during the thematic analysis of the survey responses as well as sector-wide discussions and engagement with GTAs:

Support, Training and Self-management:

- Recognise the importance of training and development opportunities and fully engage with it in order to become effective GTAs.
- Seek clear guidance on available resources and support systems.
- Make use of mentorship and opportunities for peer learning.
- Recognise prior and current experiences and skills that can inform teaching practices.
- Develop strategies for effective time management and setting of realistic expectations.

Doctoral students are not always aware of the benefits and may see teaching as additional responsibility that could detract from their research. My best advice would be that doctoral researchers should take advantage of the teaching opportunities during their doctoral studies because these can (A) provide valuable networking opportunities within your fields, (B) help to develop important communication skills, (C) provide work experience and professional skills for career development even if you do not stay in academia and (D) give you a sense of satisfaction and connection with your discipline during your PhD studies.

I would also advise doctoral researchers to take advantage of all of the training available and opportunities for recognition such as AFHEA schemes at the institution.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 2500-3000

Teaching as a Professional Development Opportunity:

- Recognise that GTA roles offer opportunities for developing communication, leadership, and pedagogical skills that are beneficial in a wide range of careers.
- Ensure that GTA experiences are documented and are acknowledged through AFHEA or equivalent recognitions.
- Engage in continuous reflection and improvement through observation, feedback, and experimentation where appropriate.

Access the available development support offered by your institution. Make good use of your mentor(s) and if you do not have one find a suitable mentor. Keep a reflective log of your teaching activities.

Pre-1992 - PGR population between 500-1000

Finding Teaching Opportunities:

- Be proactive in approaches to seeking teaching roles and exploring different types of opportunities.
- Ensure that aspirations and concerns are communicated to the PhD supervisors and other relevant stakeholders.
- Build networks and seek advice from experienced academics and peers.

It makes sense to look out for professional development opportunities in the area of learning and teaching as well as to seek out formal or informal opportunities for gaining teaching experience. Ask what is available, and don't be put off if opportunities are not forthcoming at first. It is also very helpful to observe others teaching - ask your supervisors or other staff whether they mind you sitting in on their classes. It can help to keep a reflective journal - what worked, what didn't in the sessions you observed or taught - think about small changes you could make to enhance the student experience and don't be afraid to ask the students what works for them. There is a temptation to take on any teaching and/or marking which sits well outside of your comfort zone or for which you feel you have not had the right training or support - this is not fair to the students being taught. You need to be proactive in seeking out mentorship and support

Post-1992 - PGR Population less than 500

These themes highlight the need for doctoral researchers to be proactive and communicate their needs with their supervisors, but also to expect a comprehensive support system that addresses their training needs, workload concerns, and aspirations for professional development.

6. Future Work

Through its sector-wide role in enhancing postgraduate education, the UKCGE will work with those involved in postgraduate education to promote the status of doctoral researchers who teach and encourage the adoption of the recommendations made in this report.

It will also continue to collaborate with the GTA Developers Network to support its role in providing a space for those who support and work with GTAs to share practice, collaborate to encourage collective approaches, and champion the voice of GTAs.

A future project aimed at exploring the issues and themes raised in this survey with GTAs themselves is also under consideration.

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9. Appendix

Core resources and reading materials referred to by the majority of respondents, in alphabetical order (long reading lists omitted)

Advance HE resources and frameworks

Bale & Seabrook 'Introduction to University Teaching'

EDI related papers and articles

Epigeum courses

FutureLearn

Institution's online training series or in house intro to teaching course

Institutional policy or guidance

Open University Courses

Professional Standards Framework (PSF 2023 or UKPSF 2011)

Self-generated

Textbooks relating to pedagogical approaches and theories (including diverse and international perspectives)

Vitae Researcher Development Framework

UK Council for Graduate Education,
Lichfield Centre, The Friary, Lichfield,
Staffordshire WS13 6QG.

Registered Charity No. 1061495

Email: ukcge@ukcge.ac.uk

Phone: +44 (0)1543 308 602

www.ukcge.ac.uk

X: @ukcge

Linkedin: ukcge

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